

**ACCELERATING THE PURIFICATION OF PARAFFIN IN POWDERY
ADSORBENTS USING ULTRASOUND. METHODS OF EXTRACTING
PARAFFIN AND CERESINS FROM OIL.**

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Annotation: Paraffins are refined to remove coloring and volatile matter, as well as odorous matter. Paraffin cleaning is carried out by acid-base method, using adsorbents (contact or percolation), as well as hydrocleaning. The dark color of paraffin before cleaning is explained by the presence of resinous, sulfurous, nitrogenous and other substances, as well as dark products formed from unsaturated and aromatic hydrocarbons.

Key words: Adsorbent, resinous, sulfur, nitrogenous substances, sulfuric acid, oleum, NaOH, Na₂CO₃, water, melting point, unsaturated and aromatic hydrocarbon.

Acid-base cleaning method.

One of the oldest methods of refining paraffin is to treat it with 95-98% sulfuric acid or oleum, which is 102-104% sulfuric acid. The consumption of acid or oleum varies from 0.5 to 6% by weight. Cleaning temperature 60-80⁰C. Acid Paraffin is neutralized with a 2-5% solution of NaOH, Na₂CO₃ or bleaching clay at 80-85⁰C. Neutralized paraffin is thoroughly washed with water. Cleaning is carried out periodically in mixers, paraffin is moved with compressed air with reagents. In some factories, sulfuric acid treatment is carried out by hot method at 160⁰C. Purification of sulfuric acid is very effective, the melting point of the formed solid paraffins is 48-58⁰C, the color is up to 200-250 mm according to KH-51.

Adsorption cleaning.

In some factories, paraffin adsorption cleaning is used by contact method. It is usually carried out in one of the blocks of contact oil cleaning units reconstructed for this purpose. Melted paraffin is mixed with bleaching clay, the mixture is heated to 80-150⁰C, and then the paraffin is separated from the bleaching clay in periodically operated filters. Contact purification of paraffin is relatively cheap, but only weak purification can be carried out in this way, which is paraffins that go for technical purposes. suitable for In this case, the color of paraffin usually does not exceed 50-120 mm according to KN-51. Adsorption cleaning is carried out by the percolation method, paraffin is filtered through a stationary or moving sorbent. Synthetic aluminosilicate catalyst chips, crushed bauxite, specially prepared adsorbents are used as adsorbents. In domestic percolation plants, a piece of aluminosilicate catalyst is used as an adsorbent. As the adsorbent is saturated, the next percolator is started; spent adsorbent from the first percolator is sent to regeneration. At the same time, the installation has the following disadvantages: when using raw paraffin, which has not undergone preliminary cleaning and has a strong color, the adsorbent is quickly saturated.

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